

Digital Distraction and Social Influence: Investigating Drivers of Academic Procrastination

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Abstract

Academic procrastination is often seen among adolescents, as well as among adults, includes underestimating the time limit for completing academic tasks. Students fail to complete their tasks on time due to many factors and out of which the researcher studied the role of peer pressure, use of social media etc. This study is an attempt to study the academic procrastination in relation to peer pressure and social media. The study is confined to the sample of 200 students. Simple random sampling technique is applied for the selecting sample. Analysis was done with the help of SPSS (v26), and findings revealed that academic procrastination was positively linked with social media whereas inverse relationship was found between peer pressure and academic procrastination. Further, it was indicated from the results that peer pressure and social media were significant indicator of academic procrastination.

Keywords: Peer pressure, social media, academic procrastination.

Introduction

In terms of development and education, adolescence is an importance stage of life. In this period, various activities can negatively impact one's personal and academic lives. At present social media impact is quite high and some of the adolescents are addicted to it. It has been termed a global pandemic to be more prevalent among students. Smart phone addiction leading to a high degree of dependence on the phone among adolescents while harming their physical, mental, and social functions and also students lack in managing their time for studies which develop the behaviour of delaying academic assignments (Ayadi et al., 2021, p.31). This behaviour of delaying academic assignments is known as academic procrastination which can

be termed as a tendency to put off desired academic tasks, although this can bring negative consequences.

Academic Procrastination

Procrastination cannot be separated from our everyday life as every individual procrastinate in life in one way or the other. The idea that 'I can do it later' or 'later may be better' is common illusion behind the tomorrow outlook. However, when tomorrow comes, this pattern gets repeated and so it goes on and on (Agochiya, 2010, p. 336).

Today, procrastination is very common among the students. The students' delay their daily routine activities including academic activities. Academic procrastination is an intentional delay in initiating or completing academic tasks for a certain time period or until the deadline stated by Stussi et al. (2019) (as cited in Astuti & Ariyanie, 2023, p. 392). The indicators of academic procrastination are- delaying the task or postponing the task on the next day, avoidance and pendency of the academic activities, engaging oneself in other activities rather than completing the assignments, wasting time in other activities not so important than academic works (Amin, 2019, p. 431). Procrastination in academics is generally caused by individuals who cannot control over the emotions as well as the self-indulgence in other activities i.e. unnecessary attention for the social media.

Peer Pressure: Peer pressure is another significant psychological reason and one of the causes which contributes to the academic procrastination and this pressure is neither notified nor exerted by the peers but still its effect causes a bombshell on the person. Kim and Lim (2021) observed that students with higher level of peer pressure had highest social networking sites addiction. Peer pressure, coping motives, social conformity motives were the significant predictors of social networking sites addiction.

Theoretical background

Freud's (1953) theory on procrastination stressed that individual avoid tasks that are threatening to their ego. According to Freud, procrastination is related to early childhood experiences whereas according to behaviourists, procrastination is related to reinforcement and punishment. Behaviourists theory such as classical learning theory, asserted that students who are neither rewarded after finishing the assignment on time nor punished when they delay their task completion procrastinated in life. On the other side, the cognitive theories believed that procrastination is caused by holding irrational beliefs and low self-esteem (Knaus & Ellis,

1977). One of the well-known theories, the (TMT) temporal motivation theory was given by Steel and Konig (2006) elucidated that an individual procrastinates when the task is connected with low utility and prioritize the task having high utility value. This theory stated that procrastination depends on expectancy, value, sensitivity to delay and time delay (Girdhar et al., 2020).

Peer pressure

Peer pressure is a pervasive social force that affects individuals across various stages of life, particularly during adolescence. It can significantly influence behaviour through the power of social interaction. Peer pressure is frequently observed experience affecting individuals of all ages, but in teenagers, its impact is mostly noticeable especially in educational settings. Peer pressure refers to the pressure exerted by a peer group on its members, motivating them to change their behaviours, attitudes, or values in order to fit within the group's norms. In schools, where social communications are recurrent and intimate, peer pressure found to be strongly influencing students' academic achievement, behaviour, and development (Bhujbal & Verma, 2024, p. 1).

There are both behavioural as well as identity related theories of peer pressure. Behavioural theories focussed on social learning theories (Bandura, 1977) which elucidates that one can learn by observing, watching the consequences that others receive, and modelling. According to social learning theory, individual especially adolescents feel pressure from others to do the same after observing them and conform to the group norms for being accepted within the particular group or company. On the other hand, Erickson (1950) theory of psycho-social development posits that individual development is based on his adjustment in the environment he lives, marked by different conflicts at different development stages of his life. According to Erickson's theory, at the adolescence stage which is marked by identity vs. role confusion, adolescents strive for their personal identity and are highly influenced by their peers and strive for sense of belongingness and acceptance.

Social media

Safko and Brake (2009) considered social media as “activities, practices and behaviour among communities of people who gather online to share information, knowledge and opinions using conversational media. Conversational media are web-based application that make possible for one to create and easily transmit content in the form of words, pictures, audios and videos”.

Social media is an online platform permitting its users to share, create and edit content on it, and also act as a medium through which peoples share, exchange and produce information including ideas, and other content with their virtual communities (Astuti & Ariyane, 2023, p. 393). With the passage of time, its use has become increasingly prevalent in daily life activities (Khatimah & Ryan, 2023), wherein WhatsApp (98.25%) and Youtube (91.75%) fall under the categories of highly used social networking sites (Bhandarkar et al., 2021, p. 39).

The emergence of social media has distracted the students from their studies as they constantly using it and its captivating content affects the focus towards studies and leads to academic procrastination among students (Andreassen, 2015), and also over indulgence in social networking sites is linked with procrastination, as students postpone their academic tasks while using these sites excessively as reported by Kuss and Griffiths (2011).

Peer pressure, academic procrastination, and social media usage are interlinked with each other and also influencing students' behaviour, mental health, and academic performance. Peer pressure often manifests as the influence from friends or social groups to conform to certain behaviours, which can extend to delaying tasks (procrastination) or engaging excessively with social media. Academic procrastination is a habitual postponement of academic tasks despite knowing the negative consequences, such as lower grades or increased stress. Social media platforms amplify these dynamics by providing constant exposure to peers' activities, fostering comparison, fear of missing out (FoMO), and addictive patterns that exacerbate procrastination. Research indicates these elements are particularly pronounced among adolescents and college students, where developmental sensitivities to social feedback heighten their impact.

Studies on Peer Pressure and Academic Procrastination

Peer pressure refers to the impact that peer exert on other to conform to certain norms, attitudes, behaviours, or values within a group (Brown, 2020). Multiple studies highlight how peer pressure contributes to academic procrastination, often through conformity and social influences that encourage delaying tasks. Peer pressure distracts students from doing academic activities and influences habit of procrastination in academics. A qualitative study conducted by Winingsih et al. (2017) on students of class 11th revealed that peer environment significantly influenced procrastination behaviours, students having low self-regulation and self-efficacy amplified by negative peer actions leading to delayed task completion, further analysis based on interview and observation revealed that 90% of students in certain classes exhibited

procrastination, partly due to peer dynamics that normalized postponing assignments. According to Sakthishree (2025) high peer pressure reduces motivation and increases procrastination tendencies, especially in competitive academic settings, whereas, Prasad (2017) reported that peer pressure and academic procrastination were not significantly associated with each other, likewise, Mangat (2019) also found no association between peer pressure and academic procrastination. Esen and Gundogdu (2010) found that peer pressure and academic procrastination were positively linked with each other, wherein high pressure leads to higher level of procrastination in academics. Arfah et al. (2021) found that peer conformity had positive relationship with academic procrastination with conformity to peers explaining 31.1% of contributing factor in procrastination, similarly, Irwansyah and Asrida (2021) found that peer variable significantly influence the academic procrastination, also peer interaction is negatively correlated with academic procrastination.

Studies related to Social Media and Academic Procrastination

The internet has transformed the world and become an important part of everyday life because of its endless potential (Rahmani et al., 2022). Because of students growing fixation with social media, they spend undue time on posting, scrolling, and chatting which may lead towards postponement of academic tasks (Aalbers et al., 2022; Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). A substantial body of research links social media use to increased academic procrastination, often mediated by addiction, fear of missing out (FoMO), and self-control issues. Tang and He (2025) concluded that academic procrastination was directly predicted by social media addiction with lack of self-control and fear of missing out as chain mediators between them. Gita and Dullet (2025) reported that uncontrolled surfing on social media sites along with procrastination negatively impacted students' performance in academics through distraction. The results of the study conducted by Anwar et al. (2022) demonstrated that social media usage and academic procrastination had positive correlation, it was also observed in the same study that the level of social media usage and academic procrastination was lower among postgraduate students than the undergraduate and intermediate level students. Nadarajan et al. (2023) observed that academic procrastination significantly predicted internet addiction, having 11.3% of the variance. Gong et al. (2025) found that social media usage negatively predicted academic performance through social anxiety and fear of missing out. Nwosu et al. (2020) observed that time spent on social media and number of social media sites used significantly led to internet addiction and indirectly predicted academic procrastination via internet addiction. Naushad et al. (2025) reported that 29% of the variation in academic procrastination was due to social

media addiction, further males were found to be more addicted to social media than their counterparts. Linh et al. (2024) conducted a regression analysis and results highlighted that social media, online video streaming and video games contributed 13.7% variation in the procrastination of Vietnamese students. Huanambal-Pérez et al. (2026) reported inverse relationship of the academic procrastination with academic performance while it was positively linked with internet addiction, results also indicated that internet addiction was positively linked with academic performance. Again, similar study (Huanambal-Pérez et al., 2026) internet addiction was found to played a mediating role between academic procrastination and academic performance. Fang and White (2025) conducted an interview with distance learners and explored that self-regulation, strategic planning, and learning difficulties were personal whereas study-life balance, the learning environment, and the nature of the task were external factors affecting procrastination behaviours among students wherein study-life balance was a significant contributor of predicting procrastination behaviour among distance learners. Yakut and Kuru (2020) found that there was positive and significant effect of purpose associated with using social media on academic procrastination, these results were inconsonance with Bashir (2019), Kumar (2020), and Turel and Dokimaci (2022) who found positive and significant correlation of students' usage of social networking sites with academic procrastination, contrary to these results Jerin (2021) observed no linkage between social media usage and procrastination. Caratiquit and Caratiquit (2023) found that academic procrastination is significantly influenced by social media addiction, contrary to this, Balios et al. (2024) found opposite results wherein social media addiction and academic procrastination were not significantly correlated. As per the findings of Kurajda et al. (2023) academic procrastination was predicted by negative consequences of using internet. Chandni et al. (2024), and Shaibani (2020) found that level of procrastination was increased with the rising hours of using social media. It was again concluded that students who were using social media for entertainment only procrastinated more than others, similarly, El-Ghannam and El-Hamid (2023) studied the effect of mobile phone use on academic procrastination and significant relationship was reported between excessive use of mobile phone and academic procrastination.

Studies on Peer Pressure, Social Media and their Impact on Students

Social media often amplifies peer pressure, leading to increased usage, addiction, and related behaviours like procrastination. Kimball and Cohen (2019), and American Psychological Association (2024) reported that youths' sensitivity to acceptance and rejection on social media affected their mental health as they continually busy on scrolling social media sites and also

affecting their sleeping habits, concentration on academic assignments. A review based study conducted by Yelishala (2022), and Dickerson (2024) observed that adolescents indulged in risky behaviours such as taking drugs, drinking alcohol, physical harm and also affecting their mental health due to social media which normalize the risky behaviours and make them victim of peer pressure as they tried to be accepted on social media by their peers, contrary to this, it was also observed by Yelishala (2022) that social media had some positive impacts such as, one can make friends who help in choosing better decisions, helps in expression of ideas, and a good source of entertainment. Xu et al. (2023) conducted a study on adolescents' social media addiction and the results reported that social media addiction was significantly predicted by peer pressure on mobile phone use. Further, high self-esteem and high self-concept clarity were found to be negatively related with peer pressure and social media addiction. Vente et al. (2020) reported that there were increased in the high-risk behaviours including self-harm, sexting behaviours among adolescents with the increased in number of social media sites used such as surfing on social media more than 4 social media sites and spending more than 5 hours in a day.

Objectives of the study

- To differentiate the high, average and low users of social media and peer pressure.
- To study the relationship among peer pressure, social media on academic procrastination of students.
- To predict the academic procrastination among students on the basis of peer pressure and social media usage.

Hypotheses of the study

- There is positive relationship between peer pressure and academic procrastination of students.
- There is positive relationship between the use of social media and academic procrastination of students.
- Academic procrastination can be predicted by the peer pressure and social media on individual basis as well as on collective basis.

Sample

For the present study, sample comprised of 200 students studying in 11th class of the government and private higher secondary school of Jammu district in India, which was selected by using simple random sampling technique.

Tools used in the study

- Social media scale: It was developed and standardized by the investigator consisted of 28 items. The reliability of the scale, indicated by the Cronbach alpha coefficient was of 0.74.
- Peer pressure scale: It was developed and standardized by Amandeep Kaur (2020) consisted of 36 items. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.73.
- Academic procrastination scale: It was developed and standardized by A.K. Kalia and Manju Yadav (2015) consisted of 25 items. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.82.

Data analysis

Analysis was done with the help of SPSS-26 version, correlation and multiple regression were applied for the analysis of data.

Table 1

Descriptive Analysis for the Academic Procrastination

	N	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Academic procrastination	200	-.111	.172	.237	.342
Valid N (listwise)	200				

Interpretation

It can be observed from table 1, that the value of skewness is -.111 and the value of kurtosis is .237, both of the values fall under the range of normality. Thus, as the values of both skewness and kurtosis are within the specified range, the data is said to be normally distributed.

Analysis of objective 1 To differentiate the high, average and low users of social media and peer pressure.

Table 2

Levels of Social Media

Descriptive Statistics

Dependent Variable: Academic procrastination			
Levels of Social Media Usage	Mean Sore of Academic Procrastination	Std. Deviation	N
Low Usage	72.8621	17.57580	29
Average Usage	71.3684	14.52911	152
High Usage	71.2632	10.60839	19
Total	71.5750	14.63232	200

Interpretation

The above table 2 indicates that students with low social media usage have average academic procrastination mean score of 72.8621, whereas students with average social media usage have average academic procrastination mean score of 71.3684, and students with high social media usage have average academic procrastination mean score of 71.2632. Thus, it can be interpreted that average and high social media usage students do not differ on the basis of academic procrastination scores, but there is mild variation in the academic procrastination scores of students who are low and high social media users, wherein low social media users procrastinated more in academics than high social media users.

Table 3

Levels of Peer Pressure

Dependent Variable: Academic procrastination			
Levels of Peer Pressure	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Low	64.1875	16.20789	16
Average	72.3193	14.70396	166
High	71.2778	10.91575	18
Total	71.5750	14.63232	200

Interpretation

The above table 3 shows that students with low peer pressure have average academic procrastination mean score of 64.1875, whereas students with average peer pressure have average academic procrastination mean score of 72.3193, and students with high peer pressure have average academic procrastination mean score of 71.2778. Thus, it can be interpreted that average and high peer pressure students do not differ with regards to academic procrastination scores, but there is difference in the academic procrastination scores of students with low and high peer pressure, where students with high peer pressure procrastinated more in academics than their counterparts having low peer pressure.

Analysis of objective 2 To study the relationship among peer pressure, social media on academic procrastination of students.

Table 4*Coefficient of Correlation among Academic Procrastination, Peer Pressure and Social Media*

Correlations		Academic procrastination	Social Media Usage	Peer Pressure
Pearson Correlation	Academic procrastination	1.000	.030	-.094
	Social Media Usage	.030	1.000	.849
	Peer Pressure	-.094	.849	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Academic procrastination	.	.335	.093
	Social Media Usage	.335	.	.000
	Peer Pressure	.093	.000	.
N	Academic procrastination	200	200	200
	Social Media Usage	200	200	200
	Peer Pressure	200	200	200

Interpretation

Form the above table 4 it is evident that the value of correlation between social media usage and academic procrastination is .030, which indicates the positive association of social media usage academic procrastination. Further, the correlational value between peer pressure and academic procrastination is -.094, depicting that peer pressure and academic procrastination are conversely related. Thus, hypothesis 1 is rejected and hypothesis 2 is accepted and it can be interpreted that high social media usage led to higher academic procrastination among students whereas peer pressure is inversely related with academic procrastination.

Analysis of objective 3 To predict the academic procrastination among students on the basis of peer pressure and social media usage.

Table 5

Model Summary for the Multiple Regression for the Predicators (social media and the peer pressure) and the Academic Procrastination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df 2	Sig. F Change
1	.228 ^a	.052	.042	14.31831	.052	5.412	2	197	.005

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Peer Pressure, Social Media Usage
- b. Dependent variable: Academic procrastination

Interpretation

The table 5 shows the model summary for multiple regression where R Square is 0.052, depicting 5.2% of the variation in academic procrastination is due to the peer pressure and social media usage. Thus, p-value (0.005) is significant which indicates that peer pressure and social media usage have a significant effect on academic procrastination.

Table 6

ANOVA Summary for Peer Pressure, Social Media Usage and Academic Procrastination

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2219.103	2	1109.551	5.412	.005 ^a
	Residual	40387.772	197	205.014		
	Total	42606.875	199			
a. Dependent Variable: Academic procrastination						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Peer Pressure, Social Media Usage						

Interpretation

From the table 6 it can be observed that the F value for the regression is 5.412, which is significant (p=0.005) for peer pressure, social media usage and academic procrastination. This can be observed that predictor variables (peer pressure and social media usage) significantly influence the criterion variable (academic procrastination). As the residual value is higher than

the regression value, so present model is not able to explain the lot of variances in the academic procrastination because of social media usage and peer pressure.

Table 7

Estimated Coefficients of Social Media Usage, Peer Pressure and Academic Procrastination

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	56.891	5.047		11.273	.000		
	Social Media Usage	11.785	3.929	.393	2.999	.003	.280	3.577
	Peer Pressure	-15.148	4.646	-.428	-3.261	.001	.280	3.577
a. Dependent Variable: Academic procrastination								

Interpretation

Table 7 shows the standardized beta value for social media usage is 0.393, explaining that for every one-unit change in the social media usage (independent variable), academic procrastination (dependent variable) will rise by 0.393 units. Further the standardized beta value for peer pressure is -0.428, explaining that for every one-unit change in the peer pressure (independent variable), academic procrastination (dependent variable) will decrease by -0.428 standard deviation units. The p-value for social media usage is 0.003 and peer pressure is 0.001, indicating the positive and significant correlation between social media usage and academic procrastination whereas inverse but significant correlation is found between peer pressure and academic procrastination. Thus, social media usage and peer pressure significantly predicts academic procrastination among students.

Coefficients of Multicollinearity, Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor on the basis of social media usage, peer pressure and academic procrastination

Table 7 depicts that the value of tolerance for both social media usage and peer pressure is 0.280, which is higher than 0.10, and the value for variation Inflation factor is 3.577, for both of the predictor variables (social media usage and peer pressure) which is lower than 10. For checking the multicollinearity, the value of the ‘Tolerance’ should be higher than 0.10 and the

‘Variance Inflation Factor’ should be lower than 10. Thus, issue of multicollinearity is not found in this model.

Table 8

Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted value	38.3808	61.9506	49.4250	3.33935	200
Residual	-49.16572	35.83428	.00000	14.24618	200
Std. Predicted value	-3.307	3.751	.000	1.000	200
Std. Residual	-3.434	2.503	.000	.995	200

a. Dependent variable: Academic procrastination

Figure 2

Normal Probability Plot for Normality of Residuals

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

As per the table 8 and figure 2, the mean score of the residual is 0 and standardized residual mean score and standard deviation is 0 and 0.99 which indicated normal distribution of the data. It is also observed from the figure 3, that residuals are not deviated from the straight line and are closed to the line of best fit, indicating residuals are normally distributed.

Discussion of Results

The current investigation aimed at studying the influence of peer pressure and social media usage on the academic procrastination of students. The findings reported that peer pressure and academic procrastination were inversely related, the reason behind it may be that they experienced positive peer pressure wherein students feel motivated and encouraged towards their studies in the company of peers and finish the academic assignments without any postponement, this result is corroborated by Irwansyah and Asrida (2021), and Prasad (2017), whereas, Sakthishree (2025) found opposite results as peer pressure and academic procrastination were significantly linked with each other. Another findings of this study pointed out a linkage between social media usage and academic procrastination wherein social media and academic procrastination were positively associated, the reason behind this may be that the notifications, entertaining content on social media distracts the student and due to this they delay their academic assignments, this result is in agreement with results reported by Bashir (2019), Kumar (2020), Yakut and Kuru (2020), Turel and Dokimaci (2022), Naushad et al. (2025), and Huanambal-Pérez et al. (2026) who observed significant association between social networking sites and academic procrastination. Further, findings of regression analysis reported that peer pressure and social media usage were significant contributor of academic procrastination, this conclusion is similar to the studies conducted by Arfah et al. (2021), Anwar et al. (2022), Caratiquit and Caratiquit (2023), and Tang and He (2025).

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